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Report

A Data Governance Framework for Data Sharing and its Application to a Food Supply Chain

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A Data Governance Framework for Data Sharing and its Application to a Food Supply Chain

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SUMMARY

This report presents a practical Data Governance Framework developed during the WATSON project to support secure, transparent and compliant data sharing across European food supply chains. The framework defines a template for a data governance policy with clear roles, responsibilities and processes for data providers, stewards, consumers and governance bodies, aligned with European data strategies and regulations. It integrates data quality requirements, metadata aligned with the FAIR principles, interoperability in accordance with standards, and access and usage control supported by strong security mechanisms including authentication, encryption, logging, incident handling and data sharing agreements.

The framework is demonstrated through a detailed fish supply chain traceability use case, which includes event definitions, dataset classifications and access rights matrices showing which actors may access which data and under what conditions. This example illustrates how data sovereignty can be ensured while enabling the flow of high quality, trustworthy data needed for traceability, coordination, compliance and fraud detection.

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Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Description
ABAC	Attribute-Based Access Control
API	Application Program Interface
AR	Administrative Role
CRUD	Create, Read, Update, Delete
DCAT	Data Catalog Vocabulary
DPV	Data Privacy Vocabulary
DSA	Data Sharing Agreement
EPCIS	Electronic Product Code Information Services
FAO	Food and Agriculture Organisation
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
GDST	Global Dialogue on Seafood Traceability
GLN	Global Location Number
GTIN	Global Trade Item Number
ID	Identifier
IDS	International Data Space
IDSA	International Data Space Association
IUU	Illegal, Unreported, and Unregulated
ODRL	Open Digital Rights Language
OR	Other Role
PR	Primary Role
RBAC	Role-Based Access Control
SR	Supporting Role
TLS	Transport Layer Security
TRU	Traceable Resource Unit
URL	Uniform Resource Locator

1 Introduction

The work for this report is performed under the context of WATSON (<https://watsonproject.eu/>). WATSON is a three-year EU funded research and innovation project (2023-2026) aimed at combating fraudulent practices in the food supply chain. The project advances systemic innovations that enhance transparency by strengthening traceability mechanisms, empowering authorities and policy makers with data-driven insights and increasing consumer awareness on food safety and value. The proposed WATSON solutions are tested and demonstrated through six use cases across European countries covering fish, wine, olive oil, honey, cereal and meat supply chains.

A central ambition of WATSON is to develop a holistic traceability framework that integrates data-driven services, intelligence-based toolsets and risk-estimation approaches. Achieving end-to-end traceability requires a well-defined data governance framework that ensures secure and trustworthy data sharing throughout the supply chain while upholding data sovereignty. This includes clearly established rules specifying which actors provide which data at what required quality, as well as who may access specific data under defined conditions.

1.1 Motivation

Data governance is essential for supporting data sharing required to enable traceability while safeguarding the necessary level of data sovereignty. However, there is limited knowledge about how data governance can be effectively implemented in real-world settings. The motivation for this report is therefore to examine existing work on data governance and based on this, propose a framework that supports efficient and trustworthy data sharing. The intention is for the framework to define a generic yet concrete scope and structure, and to offer practical recommendations for how data governance can be customized and configured for practical deployment in different contexts — essentially offering a “recipe” for implementation. The overarching goal is to ensure that data governance facilitates compliance through clear roles, repeatable processes, measurable outcomes and trusted data sharing, while ensuring data sovereignty, data quality, and legal compliance.

To illustrate how the framework can be applied in practice, the report includes mappings and implementation considerations using traceability in a fish supply chain as an example. These insights are drawn from our experience with the fish use case in the WATSON project.

1.2 Data Governance background and related work

The value of data increases as new technology enables more advanced knowledge generation and data-driven decision support. Data have therefore become an asset. When used effectively, data can help actors make better decisions that improve resources utilisation, detect and correct issues hampering effectiveness, compliance and sustainability, and address deviations and errors in a secure and targeted manner.

The background and related work used as input to this report includes the European strategy for data, relevant data regulations, and state-of-art in literature and European initiatives for cross sectorial data sharing.

1.2.1 European strategy for data and solutions

The European data strategy (European Commission, 2020) emphasizes the need for data sharing. A main focus has been on the establishment of what is called common European Data Spaces for sectors of importance, and much of this work is carried out based on guidelines from among others the International Data Space Association (IDSA). A data space is a distributed technical infrastructure for

the sharing of metadata on datasets, including links to the actual data that may be stored anywhere. Comprehensive security mechanisms as well as access and usage rules can be defined to ensure security, trust and reliability. Thus, IDSA emphasizes the need for data governance related to the data sharing, and relevant aspects are discussed in their IDS Reference Architecture (IDSA, 2022) and in the IDSA Rule Book (IDSA, 2020).

1.2.2 European data regulations

As an acknowledgement of the value of data, and to facilitate the data economy, a set of new European data regulations have emerged. The data governance must support compliance with these regulations, for example, the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) (EU Commission, 2016) regulates the sharing of personal data, and the Data Act (EU Commission, 2023) protects the data sovereignty and the right to data access.

1.2.3 Literature

Data governance concerns the management of data as a valuable resource (Abraham, Schneider and Vom Brocke, 2019). It encompasses policies, decisions-making processes, and responsibility related to data, including the use of standards and procedures and compliance to laws and regulations, and overarching organizational policies. (Zorrilla and Yebenes, 2022) emphasize importance of data quality and complexity, adherence to standards, data life cycle management, common vocabularies and concepts, and security mechanisms adapted to specific data types. They also highlight the need for coordination and communication between data managers and advanced data users. The Open Data Institute has studied practical implementation of data governance, including what they call data stewardship (Open Data Institute, 2023).

(Li *et al.*, 2024) observe that despite a high number of articles on Data Governance theory, there is still a lack of knowledge on the practical implementation. Based on a literature review, they adapt data governance to supply chains and highlight coordination and integration challenges, as well as data quality, as critical issues.

1.3 Definitions

Figure 1 Data Governance scope/key aspects

To facilitate understanding, we clarify the following key concepts:

- **Data governance** refers to the strategy and policy governing decision and responsibilities regarding managing and sharing of data assets. It includes mechanisms to ensure data quality, security, compliance, and appropriate use. As illustrated in Figure 1, data governance encompasses roles, responsibilities and processes for data creation/collection, management and sharing, as well as requirements concerning data content and interoperability, data quality, information security, privacy protection, regulatory and ethical compliance, and use of metadata for data profiling, description and classification in data catalogues.
- **Data stewardship** aims to unlock the value of data by ensuring that data collection, maintenance and sharing are carried out in accordance with the data governance policy. Data quality, trustworthiness and availability must be safeguarded, and the compliance with governance requirements must be continuously monitored.
- **Data sharing** refers to the exchange or dissemination of data so that it can be accessed, used, or processed by others, while maintaining the rights and sovereignties associated with the data - as defined by the data governance policy.
- **Data sovereignty** means that an individual or a legal entity retain full control of its data - including how the data are stored, shared and used, and by whom and for what purpose. This principle is supported by the European data regulations, particularly the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), the Data Act, the Data Governance Act, and the EU Cybersecurity Act. Data governance and the data sharing practices must ensure that the will and rights of the person or entity in control of the data are respected.

1.4 Content

Figure 2 provides an overview of the content of this report:

- Chapter 1 is the introduction and provides definitions and an overview of relevant literature. The definitions are aligned with European data strategies and regulations.
- Chapter 2 specifies the data governance framework. The framework is aligned with European data strategies and regulations and builds on the knowledge and definitions from Chapter 1.
- Chapter 3 describes the application of the data governance framework on a traceability use case example through a data governance policy instance.
- Chapter 4 (not in figure) is the conclusion regarding achievements and future work.

Figure 2 The content of this report

2 A Data Governance Framework

Data governance should be implemented according to a well-defined **data governance policy** that must be aligned with a data strategy that defines long-term plans and goals. The policy must define the rules to be followed and the boundaries that serve as a reference for decisions to ensure a consistent and compliant handling of the data. In general, the policy must include

- Mandatory principles for roles and responsibilities
- Mandatory principles for the processes/activities involved
- Rules to be followed to ensure data quality and security
- The terminology to be used
- Requirements regarding use of standards and compliance

The **data governance framework** addressed in this chapter, provides a template for a data governance policy by specifying generic aspects of a data governance policy. Actors and communities can use this template when establishing their own data governance policies. To be generic, the policy is based on the principle outlined in the European data strategy, European regulations, and existing data governance literature as outlined in Section 1.2.

2.1 Roles and responsibilities

There are several categories of roles addressing different dimensions of responsibilities as described in Figure 3.

- **Data governance roles** define the data governance policy and the policy implementation, and their responsibilities are defined in Table 1.
- **Data sharing roles** are responsible for the actual data sharing and use of data and for the associated infrastructures and services making this possible. Their responsibilities are defined in Table 2.
- **Use case roles** are responsible for the process steps and activities in the use case, and the roles and responsibilities will vary depending on the use case. In general, some of the actors with these roles will also be Data Providers and Data Consumers. Chapter 3 provides an example of roles from a fish supply chain of relevance to a traceability use case.

Figure 3 Overview of roles related to data governance and data sharing

Note that one actor (organisation, entity or individual) may have several roles, and a role may belong to several categories. The responsibility scope of a role may also vary, e.g. limited to one organisation, one unit within an organisation or to a domain.

Table 1 Data governance roles

Data Governance Role	Responsibility	Operational Actions
Community Data Governance Policy Manager	Define and manage community data governance policy	Define overall requirements for a community regarding data related procedures (establishment of procedures, data management procedure, documentation, etc.), problem handling, compliance, data storage, safety and security
Data Provider: Local Data Governance Policy Manager	Define and manage local data governance policy	Define which data to collect and local responsibilities, data related procedures (establishment, data management, documentation, etc.) and problem handling and requirements regarding data quality, compliance, data storage, safety and security. Contributes to the local data policy process – see 2.2.
Data Provider: Data Holder	Ensure data sovereignty aligned with policy Natural or legal person who has the right, ability, or obligation to make data available, and who exercises control over access to that data, in accordance with applicable law and data sharing agreements.	Approve the sharing of datasets, define terms and conditions for access to and use of datasets, establish Data Sharing Agreements (DSA) for datasets, sign DSAs. Contributes to the local data policy process – see 2.2

Table 2 Data sharing roles

Data Sharing Role	Responsibility	Operational Actions
Data Provider: Data Steward	Publish data with required quality, aligned with policy and Data Sharing Agreement (DSA, see Section 2.6.4)	Ensure that data quality and procedures are aligned with policy, maintain data insight and expertise, provide metadata and documentation, ensure secure data storage (may use a service provider), publish data through platform, handle feedback on data and data quality. Contributes to the data lifecycle governance process – see Section 2.2)
Data Consumer: Researcher	Access and use shared data in compliance with DSA	Discover relevant data sources, assess dataset regarding fulfilment of data needs, sign DSA, get data, use data in compliance with terms and conditions in DSA, provide feedback on data and data quality (see Section 3.2.1 for examples of use case roles)
Data Consumer: General Public		
Data Consumer: Media		
Data Consumer: Use Case Roles		

Data Sharing Role	Responsibility	Operational Actions
Data Service Provider	Offer data related services to Data Providers and Data Consumers	Provide digital knowledge and IT services, provide data related services (collection, processing, transformation, vocabularies, etc.)
Platform Operator	Operate platforms for data sharing and access	Manage platform infrastructure, offer catalogue service, manage secure platform access (user authentication and authorisation – see 2.6.1)
Data Storage Operator	Provide data storage services	Offer data storage services, manage secure access according to authorisation – see 2.6.1
Standardisation Actor	Establish data standards	Define standardisation procedures, initiate and manage standardisation processes, issue standards specifying datasets
Clearing House for Data	Economic transactions	Log and manage payments for use of datasets

Note that there is no role called “Data Owner” as the concept of ownership is not used in data legislation. When sharing data, one must instead relate to data governance policy, which will specify who has access to the data and what it may be used for.

2.2 Generic processes

The generic processes include *local data policy management* (see Table 3) and *data lifecycle governance* (see Table 4). The latter covers data capture, upload, verification, publication, archival. Automated scripts can be used to validate data and alert Data Stewards for corrections.

Table 3 Local data policy process

Local Policy Definition Stage	Operational Control	Tools and explanations
Align with Community Data Governance Policy	Local Data Governance Policy Manager gets insight into the community data policy and ensures that the organisation operates in compliance with regulations and according to relevant guidelines and requirements.	Update and sync with the community data policy updates.
Manage data assets	Local Data Governance Policy Manager ensures that the organisation identifies and manages an overview of its data assets, that all relevant data are collected and managed, that overall data quality requirements are established (see 2.3), and that the required data related responsibilities and procedures are accounted for.	Update when new datasets appear and changes to existing datasets are needed.
Manage data sovereignty	Local Data Governance Policy Manager defines in collaboration with data Stewards the data quality, access and usage policies for datasets in collaboration with Data Stewards and approves the policies.	Update when there is a need.

Local Policy Definition Stage	Operational Control	Tools and explanations
Manage data quality	Data Holder defines how to ensure required data quality (procedures, etc.) and the data quality metrics to be used. Aspects such as completeness, accuracy, timeliness, consistency and audit coverage must be addressed.	For each dataset. Update when there is a need and when quality can be improved.
Manage data sovereignty terms and conditions	Data Holder operates in accordance with the data access and usage policies and approves the sharing of datasets, defines terms and conditions for access to and use of datasets, establish Data Sharing Agreements (DSA) for datasets.	Tools exist for automatic contract negotiation and establishment (e.g., UPCAST negotiation and contracting plugin). Frameworks like GAIA-X trust framework
Approve data access	Data Holder approves Data Consumers and signs DSAs.	Tools exist for automatic contract negotiation and establishment (e.g., UPCAST negotiation and contracting plugin).

Table 4 Data lifecycle governance process

Data Life Cycle Stage	Operational Control	Frequency / Tool
Data Collection	Data Steward captures or collects data. The data collection methods and processes must be controlled and approved, and the data quality must be validated.	Real-time validation, offline sync periodically.
Data Upload	Data Steward pushes data via secure API to data storage or other channels where it can be accessed. Data structure and content are validated towards data schema.	This can be done automatically (e.g., sensor data). Continuous via event API.
Data Verification	Data Steward runs automated quality checks based on rules (completeness, timeliness, duplicates).	Triggered by upload. Validation report.
Data Publication	If the publication is approved by the Data Holder, Data Steward registers validated data in a metadata catalogue and publish the data in accordance with defined access and usage policies.	Triggered after verification.
Data Use	Data Consumer accesses data in accordance with the access and usage policy and DSAs.	Logged automatically, reports periodically.
Archival / Deletion	Data Steward ensures that data are archived or deleted as defines by its retention schedule (e.g., 5 years).	Periodic purge of expired records.

2.3 Data quality policy guidelines

The Data Steward is responsible for the data quality.

Data quality is the ability of data to satisfy its usage requirements in a given context. Data governance with a focus on data quality requires the development of a data quality policy, including definitions of

- Data quality metrics. Relevant metrics may for example address aspects such as completeness, accuracy, timeliness, consistency and audit trail coverage
- Data quality management processes, including monitoring data quality metrics and continuous measurement of data quality levels. Tools such as automated Python scripts or Power BI dashboards reading from validation APIs can be used for this purpose.
- Criteria for automated alerts to Data Stewards.

2.4 Interoperability policy guidelines

Interoperability must be provided and may cover many aspects, among other

- **Semantic aspects.** This is about the use of well-defined formats and vocabularies when data is exchanged to ensure a common understanding of the data content
- **Technical aspects.** This is about well-defined interfaces (like APIs) and services (to publish data, request data, get data, make use of services, etc.) as well as the use of well-defined communication protocols.

The “New European Interoperability Framework” (European Commission, 2017) provide further information on aspects of relevance to interoperability.

2.5 Metadata and catalogue policy guidelines

Metadata shall support the FAIR principles: data must be *Findable*, *Accessible*, *Interoperable*, and *Reusable*.

The policy must define

- The metadata to be specified and how they should be expressed. Taxonomies of relevance to the use case may be used to define a common metadata terminology. Table 5 lists some of the most relevant metadata aspects to cover.
- The catalogue in which the metadata should be registered.

Table 5 Aspects that the metadata should address

Aspect	Description	Typical metadata	Standard that may be used
Actor	Organisations/entities holding relevant roles related to the dataset (Data Holder, etc.)	Name, organisation ID, certificate, role, contact information	W3C Organisation Ontology, ISO 17442 (LEI – Legal Entity Identifier), DCAT (general metadata)
Link of relevance	Characteristics of links	ID, endpoint URL, certification status, policy compatibility, documentation,	IDS Information Model, OpenAPI (API definition), WoT TD (Thing Description)

Aspect	Description	Typical metadata	Standard that may be used
		provenance, data examples	
Description	The dataset/dataset content	Title, description, subject, keywords, format, type, license, access, terms of use, version, lifecycle	DCAT /DCAT-AP, ISO 19115 (geodata), Schema.org (structured data)
Resource	File, API endpoint, data stream source	Format (CSV, JSON, RDF, XML, etc.), MIME type, encoding, update frequency, URI, data size	DCAT, RDF (resource), Dublin Core (generic metadata), MIME RFC 2046 (content types)

2.6 Security, privacy and compliance guidelines

Data governance also covers guidelines regarding security, privacy and compliance. Ethics and compliance with standards and laws and regulations is important. In particular, privacy and ethics is crucial and may be a complex issue if personal and sensitive data is concerned. In this section, we focus on security related to access and usage guidelines, while privacy and compliance aspects are not explicitly covered.

The conditions for access to and use of data must be defined. This section presents a hybrid role- and attribute-based approach that provides a flexible and fine-grained access control. The approach is based on

- The security mechanisms in general
- The use case related roles of the Data Consumer
- The value of one of more attributes
- Data Sharing Agreements (DSAs)

2.6.1 Security mechanisms in general

Data security is about the preservation of security requirements concerning the accessibility, authenticity, availability, confidentiality, integrity, privacy, and reliability of data. The data governance policy must have a focus on data security through

- Mechanisms to be used to maintain the security – see examples in Table 6
- Risk assessments

Table 6 Security mechanisms

Relevant mechanisms	Relevant solutions/standards and established practices
Authentication	OAuth 2.0 / OpenID Connect via centralized identity provider Verifiable Credentials for verification of IDs, (automatic onboarding of actors)

Relevant mechanisms	Relevant solutions/standards and established practices
Authorization	<p>Access is allowed if the policy is satisfied. A hybrid approach combining Role-Based Access Control (RBAC) and Attribute-Based Access Control (ABAC) may be used. These approaches can also be combined with standards and technologies like Verifiable Credentials for fine-grained data access.</p> <p>Role-Based Access Control (RBAC) for coarse-grained identity. Access is granted based on who you are defined by</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Roles <p>Attribute-Based Access Control (ABAC) for fine-grained authorization: Access is granted based on the attributes of the user and the data, the action and the context. E.g.,</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • User characteristics • Dataset classification • Rules for use of dataset (actions, constraints, permissions, prohibitions, duties, etc.), e.g. as defined by Open Digital Rights Language (ODRL)¹ and the ODRL Vocabulary & Expression² • Contract/DSA reference • Time window • Geographic area • Consent status <p>A hybrid approach combining RBAC and ABAC may be used to cover both aspects.</p>
Encryption	<p>May for example require use of:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Transport Layer Security (TLS). This is a cryptographic protocol for secure communication over a computer network. It ensures privacy, data integrity, and authentication between two communicating applications. TLS is widely used in various applications (e.g. email, instant messaging, voice over IP, and HTTPS traffic on the web). • AES-256 (Advanced Encryption Standard with a 256-bit key). This is a symmetric encryption algorithm. It is widely used for securing sensitive data in storage and transmission.
Logging	<p>Access logs should be required and the retention period and review frequency should be defined. Logging for auditing and verification of data operation executions.</p>
Incident Handling	<p>The handling of security incidents should be defined, e.g. to whom such incidents should be reported, when they should be reported, and how fast the incidents should be analysed.</p>

¹ <https://www.w3.org/TR/odrl-model/>

² <https://www.w3.org/TR/odrl-vocab/#term-Action>

Relevant mechanisms	Relevant solutions/standards and established practices
	The handling may for example comply with: ISO/IEC 27035 (Information Security Incident Management), NIST Frameworks (Computer Security Incident Handling Guide).

2.6.2 Role based access control

The Data Consumer may have access rights to data that are defined by its use case related roles. Section 3.2.1 provides an example of such roles for a supply chain traceability use case.

2.6.3 Attribute based access control

Attribute-Based Access Control (ABAC) supports fine-grained and context-sensitive authorisation by evaluating attributes related to the Data Consumer, the dataset, the intended purpose of use, and the operational context. To complement the role information used in RBAC, datasets may be characterised by metadata that can be used as attributes for more flexible and precise access decisions in the Attribute-Based Access Control. Table 7 provides examples of such attributes.

Table 7 Example relevant attribute types for attribute-based access control

Attribute type	Value examples and description	
Dataset classification – independent on content	Dataset classification values	Description
	Open	Can be shared with everyone
	Shared	Can be shared based on DSA and authorisations based on roles and/or attributes Parts of the dataset might have access restrictions
	Internal	Business internal
	Confidential	Business internal and access control
	Private	Can be shared based on ID and access rights
Dataset content classification	The possible data content types have to be identified and defined. This may be a classification related to the use case or domain of relevance, e.g., measurement data and product data.	
Data quality classification	Relevant standards and general frameworks, such as ISO 8000, ISO 25012, IMF Data Quality Assessment Framework (DQAF), Total Data Quality Management (TDQM) and Data Management Body of Knowledge (DAMA DMBoK). Common dimensions include accuracy, completeness, consistency and timeliness/currentness. Other dimensions can be precision, traceability, compliance, availability, recoverability, confidentiality.	
Data value	Certain data element values or indicators may influence the access	
Purpose classification (for which the Data Consumer will use the data)	Purpose classification values	Description
	Analysis	The data will be used in analyses
	Enforcement	The data will be used by authorities in accordance with regulations
	Research	The data will be used in research
	Statistics	The data will be used to generate statistics
	Commercial use	The data will be used in commercial service or application
	Internal use	The data will be used for internal purposes
	Non-profit use	The data will be used in non-profit service or application
Public info	The data will be directly communicated or communicated in a transformed way to the public	

	Targeted info	The data will be directly communicated or communicated in a transformed way to a limited group of stakeholders
	<use case related purpose>	To be defined for specific use cases
Licence	The licence of the data. May regulate the ability to use the data for purposes not mentioned above and conditions for use	
Action categorisation	Data action group	What operations the Data Consumer may perform on the dataset
	Access	Read/View, Query/Filter, Search/Discover, Download, Stream/Subscribe
	Manipulation	Create, Update, Delete, Append, Correct. (CRUD is a subset here.)
	Sharing/distribution	Share, Transfer, Redistribute, Forward/Broker
	Processing	Analyse, Aggregate, Transform, Link/Join, Run computation, Train ML models, Simulate/Predict
	Governance & lifecycle	Classify, Validate, Approve, Audit, Archive, De-identify/Pseudonymise, Delete on request
	Security-related	Security-related: Authenticate, Authorise, Log, Encrypt/Decrypt, Monitor, Report incident.
Other conditions	Condition type value	Description
	Time constraints	The use of the data may have time constraints
	Location	Country of access, region, etc.
	Context	Contextual attributes, such as supply chain steps

2.6.4 Data Sharing Agreement (DSA)

An agreement on the use of shared data may have three parts:

1. General clauses from relevant laws and regulations and overarching policies (e.g., alignment with GDPR),
2. Specific domain or business clauses (e.g., sectoral rules, standards and community policies),
3. Concrete, dataset-specific agreement related to specific operations and purposes.

Data Sharing Agreement (DSA) template covers point 3 above. It is a formal contract that defines *how, why, and under what conditions* data can be shared between the Data Provider and the Data Consumer. It ensures that data is exchanged responsibly, securely, and in compliance with legal, sector-specific and organizational requirements. A DSA can combine a human-readable contract with a machine-readable part that defines policies or rules for automated enforcement building upon standards such as:

- **Open Digital Rights Language (ODRL)** (<https://www.w3.org/TR/odrl-model/>). This is a W3C standard policy language that defines, manages and enforces machine-readable rules (e.g., permission, prohibitions and obligations) for controlling the use of digital content, data and services.
- **Data Privacy Vocabulary (DPV)** (<https://w3c.github.io/dpv/2.2/dpv/>). This is a W3C semantic framework that provides a standardized, interoperable, machine-readable vocabulary for representing privacy, personal data processing, and legal compliance.

A DSA may, for instance, define:

- Agreement ID
- Scope and definitions
- Dataset ID
- Description of dataset
 - Short description of the data content, e.g. data fields
 - Metadata, e.g. # entries, geographical coverage, time period, ...
 - Disclaimer on accuracy, completeness, integrity, and reliability of the data

- Parties involved and contacts
 - Data Holder with data sovereignty + contact information
 - Data Consumer (must be authenticated)
- Purpose for data use
 - The permitted purposes of use and relevant fees/price model
- Time period for agreement/Retention
- Permitted actions and restrictions
- Fine-grained permission, prohibitions (e.g., onward transfer or share), and duties in human-readable and machine-readable (ODRL/DPV) form, e.g.: liabilities using ODRL vocabulary:
 - Permitted purposes (e.g., traceability, compliance, research)
 - Restrictions on use (e.g. commercial use, sharing with third parties, ...)
 - Duties in agreement period (e.g. report errors in dataset, ...)
 - Duties at end of agreement period (e.g. delete dataset, stop use of dataset, ...)
- General obligations
 - Provider: accuracy / up-to-date data
 - Consumer: compliance, e.g., no onward disclosure with consent or lawful basis
- Security and data sharing mechanisms
 - State-of-the-art technical and organisational measures, such as secure data transfer, comprehensive transfer logs, encryption in transit
 - Data protection requirements (storage, transfer, notifications in case of a breach, etc.)
- Other terms
 - Data licence information (rights, third parties, etc.)
 - Fee/price information
 - Agreement termination conditions
 - Transfer cost responsibilities
 - Ethical standards to be followed
 - Confidentiality
 - Governing laws, jurisdiction and dispute resolution
 - Signature and appendices

3 Date Governance Framework applied on an example use case

The data governance framework described in Chapter 2 provides a template for a data governance policy by specifying generic aspects of such a policy. Actors and communities can use this template when establishing their own data governance policies.

This chapter applies the data governance framework from Chapter 2 to establish a data governance policy for an end-to-end traceability use case for a fish supply chain studied in the WATSON project. The policy includes:

- Use case roles, responsibilities and processes aligned with the use case
- Data quality rules
- Interoperability and metadata rules
- Dataset classification rules
- Purpose classification rules
- Access and usage rules

3.1 Traceability use case

In this use case, traceability data is intended to be shared among actors in the fish supply chain. The actors have data on their operations, and some of these data may also be useful to other actors in the supply chain, e.g. for coordination purposes, awareness about the products that are received, handled or processed, deviation detection and handling, and documentation of compliance with rules and regulations. Thus, data will be shared while maintaining data security and sovereignty.

3.1.1 Process steps

Figure 4 An example of a generic fish supply chain with possible steps.

Figure 4 illustrates possible process steps for the fish supply chain. As described in (Natvig, Jiang and Ræder, 2026 (in prep.)), the steps are:

- **Sourcing:** Starts when catch starts. Ends when catch is available for the next process step
- **Landing:** Starts with the landing of pallets. Ends when all pallets are landed and ready for the next process step
- **Transport:** Starts with the load unit pickup. Ends with delivery of load unit to intermediate or final destination.
- **Export/Import:** Starts with an initiation of trade item export/import. Ends when a custom clearance is provided
- **Trading:** Starts with an initiation of raw material sales process. Ends when sales contracts are established
- **Storage:** Starts with reception of a load unit/product item at storage/wholesaler’s location. Ends when the load unit/product item is handed over to carrier for transport

- **Transfer:** Starts when the movement of a load unit or product item starts. Ends when load unit or product item is moved and ready for the next process step
- **Processing:** Starts with reception of bulk/trade items that are inputs to the production of new trade items. Ends when new product items are identified and ready for the next process step
- **Retailing:** Starts when product item is received by Retailer. Ends when sold product is delivered to customer

3.1.2 Event types

Events of different types may occur within the process steps. Each event is related to one or more Traceable Resource Units (TRUs), which may be logistic units or products that flow through the supply chain. The event types are

- **Aggregation:** Covers aggregation, de-aggregation and transformations of TRUs and related TRU commissioning. May cover re-labelling of a TRU, packing, re-packing, consolidation, splitting, and linkage of the TRU to devices/systems (e.g. sensor devices)
- **Deviation:** A deviation is detected regarding a TRU or a process step (e.g. transport)
- **Export/Import:** May indicate that a trade item or bulk is imported or exported and that a customs clearance is issued
- **Measurement:** May for example cover status or condition of a TRU or TRU environment
- **Processing:** Raw material and/or input products are processed or transformed to a new product
- **Quality Inspection:** The result of an inspection of a TRU or a process step is registered
- **Receiving:** The delivery of a TRU to the current process step is registered
- **Rest material:** The input product/raw material is not fully used and there is Rest material
- **Sales:** The sale of a TRU (a bulk load, product or trade item) is registered
- **Shipping:** The shipping request for TRU(s) from one location to another is issued
- **Sourcing:** Commissioning of catch/crop of one particular type of raw material
- **Transport:** May indicate that a TRU is picked up or delivered at a location
- **Waste:** The processing generates waste material.

3.1.3 Data model

For each event, event information, as specified by the overall information model in Figure 5, is registered. The model is based on the traceability framework proposed by (Natvig, Jiang and Ræder, 2026 (in prep.)). The model reuses GS1 data elements (stereotyped with “EPCIS” and “eCom”) from (GS1, 2012, 2013, 2017, 2022).

Figure 5 Information content on events

Assumptions/requirements for an end-to-end traceability system:

- For this supply chain, all traceability events for the end-to-end traceability should be registered by the actor that performs the process step in which the event occur. The event should as far as possible be automatically registered.
- When creating an event, the event type will be selected, then the event ID, time and location will be generated/entered automatically by the system and cannot be altered later
- An event cannot be deleted or altered after creation (such as done for blockchain) or it is allowed to update certain fields, i.e., to decide which alternatives to use for implementation - a: on the original record, b: only new records with the updated information are added, the old ones are not deleted/altered.
- The supply chain actors have access to the tracked information about the events, but not necessarily to information on all events and to details on the TRUs and the events (represented by the TRUDetails and EventDetails classes in the information model).

3.2 Supply Chain roles and actors

3.2.1 Supply chain roles

Figure 6 Supply chain roles with relations to data governance roles and data sharing roles

Figure 6 show the supply chain roles of relevance to the traceability use case as well as the generic data governance and data sharing roles defined in Section 2.1. The supply chain roles are divided into

- Roles that actively contribute to the supply chain – see definition of the roles in Table 8.
- Roles that have stake in the supply chain, but they do not actively participate - see definition of the roles in Section 2.1.

Table 8 Roles that actively contribute to the supply chain

Supply Chain Role	Responsibility	Operational Actions	Examples of links to other roles
Raw Material Provider	Catching, cultivation and/or harvesting Product quality	Obtain and deliver raw materials in compliance with regulations, ethics and other requirements	Data Sharing role: Data Provider
Trader	Sale of raw materials, food products or feed	Negotiate terms and conditions, direct sale, auction, retail	Data Sharing role: Data Provider
Exporter/Importer	Export/import food products in accordance with regulations	Organise export/import, provide input to and follow up customs	Data Sharing roles: Data Provider, Data Consumer

Supply Chain Role	Responsibility	Operational Actions	Examples of links to other roles
Transport Service Provider	Transport logistics and transport operations	Set up, coordinate and follow up transport chains, manage and execute transport operation, ensure compliance with regulations	Data Sharing role: Data Provider
Storage Provider	Storage facilities and services	Operate storage facilities, provide storage services	Data Sharing role: Data Provider, Data Consumer
Processor	Production of food products Product quality	Process food raw materials/products to produce new products, packing & labelling of food products, ensure compliance with regulations and ethics, ensure food safety, ensure traceability	Data Sharing roles: Data Provider, Data Consumer
Quality Inspector	Quality assessments according to rules	Assess food raw materials and products, assess methods and procedures used, approve quality and compliance	Data Sharing roles: Data Provider, Data Consumer
Retailer	Retail business Product quality	Offers of products to Consumers	
Consumer	Consumes food products	Consumes food products	Data Sharing role: Data Consumer

Table 9 Roles that have interest in the supply chain

Supply Chain Role	Responsibility	Operational Actions	Examples of links to other roles
Authority	Enforcement of regulations	Receive and process reports, control and inspect, and enforce	Data Sharing roles: Data Provider, Data Consumer
Regulator	Laws and regulations	Establishment of laws and regulations	

3.2.2 Supply chain actors

Table 10 shows how the supply chain roles defined in Section 3.2.1 and the generic data governance and data sharing roles defined in Section 2.1 are mapped to the fish supply chain actors in the traceability use case.

Some comments to the table:

- The Community Data Governance Policy Manager role is not yet implemented. There is a need for a traceability coordinator that can take this role.

- The Transport Service Provider is not identified as several transport operators may be used
- The Quality Inspectors, Data Service Provider and Clearing House for Data are not identified as several actors may have these roles.
- The Platform Operator, Data Storage Operator and Standardisation Actor roles may fulfilled be several actors, and (X) indicates that this is one of several examples.
- The responsibility scope of the actors with the Community Data Governance Policy Manager may vary, as indicated in the table.

Table 10 Mapping of roles to actors in the fish supply chain

Roles	Actors							
	Hermes	Råfisklaget	Troms fryseterminal	Espersen	ScanFish	Fiskeridirektoratet	Mattilsynet	Traceability coordinator (new)
Supply chain roles – see details in Section 3.2.1								
Raw Material Provider	X							
Trader		X			X			
Exporter/importer					X			
Transport Service Provider								
Storage Provider			X					
Processor				X				
Quality Inspector								
Authority						X	X	
Data sharing roles - see details on responsibilities and actions for the role in Section 2.1 and 2.2								
Data Provider: Data Steward	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	
Data Consumer		X	X	X	X	X	X	
Data Service Provider								
Platform Operator						(X)		
Data Storage Operator						(X)		-
Standardisation Actor						(X)	(X)	
Clearing House for Data								
Data governance roles - see details on responsibilities and actions for the role in Section 2.1 and 2.2								
Community Data Governance Policy Manager						Defines requirements related to sustainability (quota, regulation compliance (e.g. IUU fishing)) Define traceability requirements	Defines requirements related to food safety (quality aspects, fine-grained end-to-end traceability)	Coordinate traceability approach in supply chain
Data Provider: Local Data Governance Policy Manager	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	
Data Provider: Data Holder	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	

3.3 Data quality rules

Table 11 provides an overview of quality metrics related to the data in the event datasets. The frequency indicates how often the metric values should be updated and assessed. Automated alerts can be sent to data stewards when metrics drop below target threshold.

Table 11 Examples of quality related metrics.

Metric	Definition	Target	Frequency
Completeness	% of mandatory fields filled	≥ 95%	Weekly
Accuracy	% data passing logical and range checks	≥ 98%	Weekly
Timeliness	Data uploaded within 24h of catch	≥ 90%	Daily
Consistency	No conflicting identifiers (e.g. batch ID, vessel ID)	100%	Weekly
Audit Trail Coverage	% of events with trace logs	100%	Continuous

3.4 Interoperability and metadata rules

Relevant data standards for interoperability may for example includes GDST 1.1, GS1 EPCIS/CBV, ISO 22005, FAO CWP codes, and RDF/OWL ontologies for semantic interoperability, and metadata based on DCAT-AP exposed through a CKAN catalogue.

Domain	Standard	Implementation Tool
Traceability	GS1 EPCIS GDST 1.1 (Key Data Elements & Critical Tracking Events)	JSON-LD or GS1 EPCIS message schema
Identifiers	GS1 GLN/GTIN, FAO vessel & species codes	Reference master data service
Food & Feed Traceability	ISO 22005	Compliance audit checklist
Semantic Interoperability	W3C RDF/OWL Ontology	Ontology API for linked data export
Metadata	DCAT-AP (Data Catalogue Vocabulary)	Metadata repository + CKAN front-end

For traceability, not all details of relevance are covered by the standards, and the WATSON project has defined detailed data models defining the content of each event type to cover such aspects.

3.5 Dataset classification rules

The datasets to be shared contain data on the events that have occurred, and there is one dataset type for each event type listed in Section 3.1.2.

3.5.1 Dataset classification independent of content

Traceability is about data sharing and based on the examples provided in Section 2.6.3, all datasets are classified as “shared”.

3.5.2 Dataset content classification

Datasets should be classified based on their content (see Section 2.4). The table below shows relevant content-based classifications of the data of relevance to the traceability use case, with references to elements in the data model in Figure 5 in Section 3.1.3, the event types that provide the data content, and the data provider.

Table 12 Content-based classification of data

Content classification	Detailed data elements in data model (see Figure 5)	Event type (see 3.1.2)	Data Provider (Actor/Role)
Aggregation data	Details - if raw materials: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • TRUDetails on raw material product Details - if device (e.g. sensor) is attached <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EventDetails 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Aggregation 	Any actor/role
Catch data	Details: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • TRUDetails – data on catch, species, gear, license, quota, etc. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sourcing 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Hermes/Raw Material Provider
Deviation data	Details: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EventDetails – Data on deviation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Deviation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Hermes/Raw Material Provider • Transport Service Provider • Espersen/Processor • Retailer
Event data	Overall information: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • TRU – ID of involved TRUs and data on product quantity, batch and serial numbers, etc. • CriticalTrackingEvent – event type, date, etc. • TransactionalParty - Actors/locations • Ecom_DocumentReference – relevant references 	All event types	Any actor/role
Export/Import data	Details: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • None. Event data covers everything 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Export/Import 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ScanFish (contract)/ Trader
Fishing vessel data	Details: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • TRUDetails – data on vessel, license, quota, etc. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sourcing 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Hermes/ Raw Material Provider
Landing data	Details: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • None. Event data covers everything 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Receiving 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Råfisklaget (auction)/Trader
Measurement data	Details: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EventDetails – data on actual measurements 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Measurement 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Hermes/Raw Material Provider • Troms fryseterminal/Storage Provider • Espersen/Processor
Processing/ Production data	Details: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • TRUDetails – data on processing methods • EventDetails – processing information 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Processing 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Hermes/Raw Material Provider • Espersen/Processor
Product data	Details: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • TRUDetails – data on product name, brans, quality, packing, brand, ... 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Aggregation • Export/Import • Processing • Receiving • Sourcing • Transport 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Hermes/Raw Material Provider • Espersen/Processor

Content classification	Detailed data elements in data model (see Figure 5)	Event type (see 3.1.2)	Data Provider (Actor/Role)
Quality inspection (QI) data	Details: • EventDetails – data on inspection and results	• Quality inspection	• Hermes/ Raw Material Provider • Råfisklaget (auction)/Trader • Espersen/ Processor
Rest material data	Details: • None. Event data covers everything	• Rest material	• Espersen/ Processor
Receiving data	Details: • None. Event data covers everything	• Receiving	• Troms fryseterminal/Storage Provider • Espersen/ Processor • Retailer
Sales data	Details: • None. Event data covers everything	• Sales	• Råfisklaget (auction)/Trader • ScanFish (contract)/ Trader • Espersen/ Processor
Shipping data	Details: • None. Event data covers everything	• Shipping	• Råfisklaget (auction)/Trader • ScanFish (contract)/ Trader
Storage data	Details: • TRUData on storage instructions	• Receiving	• Troms fryseterminal/ Storage Provider
Transshipment data	Details: • None. Event data covers everything	• Receiving	• Hermes/ Raw Material Provider
Transport data	Details: • TRUData – data on transport instructions	• Transport	• Råfisklaget (auction)/Trader • ScanFish (contract)/ Trader
Waste data	Details: • EventDetails – data on amount	• Waste	• Espersen/ Processor

Table 13 provides a classification of the content for each event type, with refinances to the content types in Table 12 and details on the overall data content (common to all event types) and the detailed data content for each event type.

Table 13 The data content for each event type

Event type (see 3.1.2)	Content classification	Overall data (O) (see Figure 5)	Detailed data (D) (see data elements in data model)
Aggregation	Aggregation data Product data	Overall event data: • TRU – ID of involved TRUs and data on product quantity, batch and serial numbers, etc. • CriticalTracking Event – event type, date, etc. • TransactionalParty - Actors/ locations • Ecom_DocumentReference – relevant references	Details - if raw materials: • TRUDetails – data on product name, brans, quality, packing, brand, ... • TRUDetails on raw material product Details - if device (e.g. sensor) is attached • EventDetails - device
Export/Import	Export/Import data Product data		Details: • TRUDetails – data on product name, brans, quality, packing, brand, ...
Measurement	Measurement data		Details: • EventDetails – data on actual measurements
Processing	Processing/ Production data Product data		Details: • TRUDetails – data on product name, brans, quality, packing, brand, ... • TRUDetails – data on processing methods • EventDetails – processing information
Quality inspection	Quality inspection (QI) data		Details: • EventDetails – data on inspection and results
Receiving	Landing data Product data Storage data Transshipment data		Details: • TRUDetails – data on product name, brand, quality, packing, brand, ... • TRUData on storage instructions
Rest material	Rest material data		No details

Event type (see 3.1.2)	Content classification	Overall data (O) (see Figure 5)	Detailed data (D) (see data elements in data model)
Sales	Sales data		No details
Shipping	Shipping data		No details
Sourcing	Catch data Fishing vessel data Product data		Details: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • TRUDetails – data on catch, species, gear, license, quota, etc. • TRUDetails – data on vessel, license, quota, etc. • TRUDetails – data on product name, brands, quality, packing, brand, ...
Transport	Product data Transport data		Details: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • TRUData – data on transport instructions • TRUDetails – data on product name, brands, quality, packing, brand, ...
Waste	Waste data		Details: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EventDetails – data on amount

3.6 Purpose classification rules

A use case related purpose for access to datasets are defined in Table 14. The generic purposes defined in Section 2.6.3 are also relevant.

Table 14 Example of use case related purpose for access to dataset

Purpose	Comment
Traceability	The Data Consumer will use the data for supply chain coordination and for tracing logistic units or products through the supply chain

3.7 Access and usage rules

As described in Section 2.6, the authorisation to access and use data may depend on the use case related role of the Data Consumer (role-based access control - see Section 2.6.2) and attributes (attribute-based access control - see Section 2.6.3) as well as security mechanisms. For the traceability use case, these approaches are combined. The access and usage access rules build on:

- Roles classifying the actors involved (see Section 3.2).
- Dataset content classification (see Section 3.5.2). The content independent classification (see Section 3.5.1) can be neglected since all dataset types are classified as “shared”.
- Action categories (see Table 7)
- Purpose for which the data will be used and other usage constraints

3.7.1 Security mechanisms to be used

Table 15 lists the required security mechanisms to be used, based on the general guidelines in Section 2.6.1.

Table 15 Security mechanisms to be used for the use case

Mechanisms	Relevant solutions/standards and established practices
Authentication	OAuth 2.0 / OpenID Connect via centralized identity provider
Authorization	Access is allowed if the access rules are satisfied, and a hybrid approach combining RBAC and ABAC should be used.

Mechanisms	Relevant solutions/standards and established practices
Encryption	TLS for transport, AES-256 for data at rest
Logging	Access logs retained 12 months, reviewed monthly
Incident Handling	ISO/IEC 27035 should be followed. Security incidents reported within 24h, root cause analysis within 5 days.

3.7.2 Access and usage rules

To simplify the elaboration of the access rules with respect to roles and actors, the supply chain roles may be divided into primary, secondary, administrative and other roles.

Primary Roles (PR) have an overall responsible for product quality. PRs include the following roles:

- Raw Material Providers
- Processors
- Retailers

As Data Consumers, PRs need access to details regarding relevant process steps that enable them to

- Verify compliance to regulations and ethics
- Detect and prevent fraud and conditions and situation in previous and subsequent process steps that may affect the safety or the quality of the products
- Take required actions, e.g. withdrawals and/or notifications of other supply chain actors
- Detect inefficiencies in the supply chain that affects their operations

Supporting Roles (SR) carry out actions that might affect the products. They are responsible for the provision of services according to the requirements and do not affect the product quality and safety in any way. They are however not responsible for actual products. SRs include the following roles:

- Transport Service Providers
- Storage Providers

SRs must have access to data that enable them to

- Carry out their activities as required and verify that this is done
- Notify other parts of the supply chain in case they detect deviations that might affect product quality or safety

Administrative Roles (AR) do not handle the physical products and cannot affect the quality and safety.

ARs include the following roles:

- Trader
- Importer/Exporter
- Quality Inspector

ARs must have access to data that enable them to

- Carry out their administrative tasks
- Document that tasks they have carried out

Other Roles (OR) are outside the supply chain and will have access to data according to their role. The ORs have the following roles:

- Consumer/Public. They get access to data on the product and how it is established
- Authority. They get access to data as defined by regulations, mainly through report.

Table 16 provides an overview of the rights with respect to traceability data from the different process steps and event types. A combination of a role- and attribute-based approach is used. For the latter, the action categorisation attributes under the access and manipulation action groups defined in Table 7 in Section 2.6.3 define what actors with specific roles can do with datasets, using the CRUD indicators:

- **C - create.** The Data Provider in the Data Holder's organisation (e.g. represented by the Data Steward role) may typically have this type of action
- **R - read.** Data Consumers typically have this type of action as well as the Data Provider.
- **U - update.** The Data Steward in the Data Holder's organisation may typically have this type of action
- **D - delete.** The Data Provider in the Data Holder's organisation (e.g. represented by the Data Steward role) may have this type of action

The above indicators are used with references to the overall data (O) and detailed data (D). "R: O+D" means that the actor can read overall and detailed data. "R: O" means that just overall data can be read.

The data content classification and the related overall and detailed data are defined in Section 3.5.2. In general:

- **Primary roles** must in general have access to all details.
- **Supporting roles** will in general not have access to detailed event data, just overall event data that can support coordination with previous step and notifications (e.g. in case of events that may cause problems in succeeding steps).
- **Administrative roles** should have access to details of relevance to their responsibilities.
- **Quality inspectors** must have access to detailed event data from most steps as they must consider how previous events might have affected the quality of products.
- **Actors responsible for shipping events** (i.e. transport bookings) need detailed data on the transport to be able to follow up.
- **Data on shipping events** (i.e. the booking of transports) are not widely shared as they are considered as less relevant to most actors.
- **Data on rest material, sales and shipping events** have just overall data, no details.
- **Data on sales event** are not sensitive information as there are no price information, consequently, data on sales can be shared so the product owner is known.

Table 16 Traceability data source access and usage policy example illustrated using the CRUD (Create, Read, Update, Delete) operations from the action categories defined in Table 7 (data manipulation actions).

Supply chain roles & Actors			Raw Material Provider (PR): Hermes	Transport Service Provider (SR): Råfisklaget	Trader (AR) auction: Råfisklaget	Trader (AR) contract: ScanFish	Exporter/Importer (AR): ScanFish	Transport Service Provider (SR): -	Storage Provider (SR):Troms fryse-terminal	Processor (PR): Espersen	Quality Inspector (AR): -	Retailer (PR): -	Consumer /Public (OR): -	Authority (OR): Fiskeri-direktoratet/Mattilsynet
Process step	Event type	Data content classification	Allowed action (CRUD: C=Create, R=Read, U=Update, D=Delete) on overall (O) or detailed (D) data											
Sourcing	Sourcing	Catch data	CRUD: O+D	R: O	R: O+D	R: O+D	R: O+D	R: O	R: O	R: O+D	R: O+D	R: O+D	R: O+D	R: O+D Report
		Fishing vessel data	CRUD: O+D	R: O	R: O+D	R: O+D	R: O+D	R: O	R: O	R: O+D	R: O+D	R: O+D	R: O+D	
		Product data	CRUD: O+D	R: O	R: O+D	R: O+D	R: O+D	R: O	R: O	R: O+D	R: O+D	R: O+D	R: O+D	
	Aggregation	Aggregation data	CRUD: O+D	R: O	R: O+D	R: O+D	R: O+D	R: O	R: O	R: O+D	R: O+D	R: O+D	R: O+D	
		Product data	CRUD: O+D	R: O	R: O+D	R: O+D	R: O+D	R: O	R: O	R: O+D	R: O+D	R: O+D	R: O+D	
	Measurement	Measurement data	CRUD: O+D	R: O	R: O+D	R: O+D	R: O+D	R: O	R: O	R: O+D	R: O+D	R: O+D	R: O+D	
Quality Inspection (QI)	QI data	R: O+D	R: O	R: O+D	R: O+D	R: O+D	R: O	R: O	R: O+D	CRUD: O+D	R: O+D	R: O+D		
Landing	Receiving	Landing data	R: O+D	CRUD: O+D	R: O	R: O	R: O	R: O	R: O	R: O+D	R: O+D	R: O+D		R: O+D Report
		Product data	R: O+D	CRUD: O+D	R: O	R: O	R: O	R: O	R: O	R: O+D	R: O+D	R: O+D		
	Aggregation	Aggregation data	R: O+D	CRUD: O+D	R: O	R: O	R: O	R: O	R: O	R: O+D	R: O+D	R: O+D		
	Measurement	Measurement data	R: O+D	CRUD: O+D	R: O	R: O	R: O	R: O	R: O	R: O+D	R: O+D	R: O+D		
	QI	QI data	R: O+D	R: O+D	R: O	R: O	R: O	R: O	R: O	R: O+D	CRUD: O+D	R: O+D		
	Deviation	Deviation data	R: O+D	CRUD: O+D	R: O	R: O	R: O	R: O	R: O	R: O+D	R: O+D	R: O+D		
Trading	Sales	NA	R: O	R: O	CRUD: O-1	CRUD: O-2	R: O-1/2	R: O	R: O-1/2	R: O	R: O	R: O		
	Shipping	Shipping data	R: O	R: O	CRUD: O-1	CRUD: O-2	R: O-1/2	R: O-1/2	R: O-1/2	R: O	R: O	R: O		
Transport	Transport	Product data	R: O+D		R: O	R: O+D	R: O	CRUD: O+D	R: O	R: O+D	R: O+D	R: O+D		
		Transport data	R: O+D		R: O	R: O+D	R: O	CRUD: O+D	R: O	R: O+D	R: O+D	R: O+D		
	Measurement	Measurement data	R: O+D		R: O	R: O+D	R: O	CRUD: O+D	R: O	R: O+D	R: O+D	R: O+D		

Supply chain roles & Actors			Raw Material Provider (PR): Hermes	Transport Service Provider (SR): Råfisklaget	Trader (AR) auction: Råfisklaget	Trader (AR) contract: ScanFish	Exporter/Importer (AR): ScanFish	Transport Service Provider (SR): -	Storage Provider (SR):Troms fryse-terminal	Processor (PR): Espersen	Quality Inspector (AR): -	Retailer (PR): -	Consumer /Public (OR): -	Authority (OR): Fiskeri-direktoratet/Mattilsynet
Process step	Event type	Data content classification	Allowed action (CRUD: C=Create, R=Read, U=Update, D=Delete) on overall (O) or detailed (D) data											
	Deviation	Deviation data	R: O+D		R: O	R: O+D	R: O	CRUD: O+D	R: O	R: O+D	R: O+D	R: O+D		
Storage	Receiving	Product data	R: O+D	R: O				R: O	CRUD: O+D	R: O+D	R: O+D	R: O+D		
		Storage data	R: O+D	R: O				R: O	CRUD: O+D	R: O+D	R: O+D	R: O+D		
	Aggregation	Aggregation data	R: O+D	R: O				R: O	CRUD: O+D	R: O+D	R: O+D	R: O+D		
		Product data	R: O+D	R: O				R: O	CRUD: O+D	R: O+D	R: O+D	R: O+D		
	Measurement	Measurement data	R: O+D	R: O				R: O	CRUD: O+D	R: O+D	R: O+D	R: O+D		
	Shipping	Shipping data	R: O	R: O	R: O	R: O	R: O	R: O	CRUD: O	R: O	R: O	R: O		
Transport (one or more)	Transport	Product data	R: O+D					CRUD: O+D	R: O+D	R: O+D	R: O+D	R: O+D		
		Transport data	R: O+D					CRUD: O+D	R: O+D	R: O+D	R: O+D	R: O+D		
	Measurement	Measurement data	R: O+D					CRUD: O+D	R: O+D	R: O+D	R: O+D	R: O+D		
	Deviation	Deviation data	R: O+D					CRUD: O+D	R: O+D	R: O+D	R: O+D	R: O+D		
Transfer (Zero or more)	Receiving	Product data	R: O+D					CRUD: O+D	R: O+D	R: O+D	R: O+D	R: O+D		
		Transshipment data	R: O+D					CRUD: O+D	R: O+D	R: O+D	R: O+D	R: O+D		
	Aggregation	Aggregation data	R: O+D					CRUD: O+D	R: O+D	R: O+D	R: O+D	R: O+D		
		Product data	R: O+D					CRUD: O+D	R: O+D	R: O+D	R: O+D	R: O+D		
	Measurement	Measurement data	R: O+D					CRUD: O+D	R: O+D	R: O+D	R: O+D	R: O+D		
	QI	QI data	R: O+D					R: O+D	R: O+D	R: O+D	CRUD: O+D	R: O+D		
Deviation	Deviation data	R: O+D					CRUD: O+D	R: O+D	R: O+D	R: O+D	R: O+D			
Export/Import (Zero or one)	Export/Import	Export/Import data	R: O+D					CRUD: O+D	R: O	R: O	R: O+D	R: O+D		R: O+D Reports
		Product data	R: O+D					CRUD: O+D	R: O	R: O	R: O+D	R: O+D		
Processing	Receiving	Product data	R: O+D					R: O	R: O	CRUD: O+D	R: O+D	R: O+D		

Supply chain roles & Actors			Raw Material Provider (PR): Hermes	Transport Service Provider (SR): Råfisklaget	Trader (AR) auction: Råfisklaget	Trader (AR) contract: ScanFish	Exporter/Importer (AR): ScanFish	Transport Service Provider (SR): -	Storage Provider (SR):Troms fryse-terminal	Processor (PR): Espersen	Quality Inspector (AR): -	Retailer (PR): -	Consumer /Public (OR): -	Authority (OR): Fiskeri-direktoratet/Mattilsynet
Process step	Event type	Data content classification	Allowed action (CRUD: C=Create, R=Read, U=Update, D=Delete) on overall (O) or detailed (D) data											
Process	Aggregation	Aggregation data	R: O+D					R: O	R: O	CRUD: O+D	R: O+D	R: O+D		
		Product data	R: O+D					R: O	R: O	CRUD: O+D	R: O+D	R: O+D		
	Processing	Processing/production data	R: O+D					R: O	R: O	CRUD: O+D	R: O+D	R: O+D		
		Product data	R: O+D					R: O	R: O	CRUD: O+D	R: O+D	R: O+D		
	Measurement	Measurement data	R: O+D					R: O	R: O	CRUD: O+D	R: O+D	R: O+D	R: O+D	
	QI	QI data	R: O+D					R: O	R: O	R: O+D	CRUD: O+D	R: O+D	R: O+D	
	Deviation	Deviation data	R: O+D					R: O	R: O	CRUD: O+D	R: O+D	R: O+D	R: O+D	
	Rest material	Rest material data	R: O					R: O	R: O	CRUD: O	R: O	R: O	R: O	
	Wast	Wast data	R: O+D					R: O	R: O	CRUD: O+D	R: O+D	R: O+D	R: O+D	
	Shipping	Shipping data	R: O					R: O	R: O	CRUD: O	R: O	R: O	R: O	
Sales	Sales data	R: O					R: O	R: O	CRUD: O	R: O	R: O	R: O		
Transport	Transport	Product data	R: O+D					CRUD: O+D	R: O+D	R: O+D	R: O+D	R: O+D		
		Transport data	R: O+D					CRUD: O+D	R: O+D	R: O+D	R: O+D	R: O+D		
	Measurement	Measurement data	R: O+D					CRUD: O+D	R: O+D	R: O+D	R: O+D	R: O+D		
	Deviation	Deviation data	R: O+D					CRUD: O+D	R: O+D	R: O+D	R: O+D	R: O+D		
Retailing	Receiving	Product data	R: O+D							R: O+D		CRUD: O+D		
	QI	QI data	R: O+D							R: O+D	CRUD: O+D	R: O+D		
	Deviation	Deviation data	R: O+D							R: O+D		CRUD: O+D		
	Sales	Sales data	R: O+D							R: O+D		CRUD: O+D		

Other rules can define how the data can be used by the Data Consumers that have access to the data. This can be defined by the purpose classification values and the other condition values provided in Section 2.6.3. Table 17 provides an example adapted to the traceability use case. In general, all supply chain actors need the data for traceability purposes. In addition, the Processor may also want to do analyses to be able to improve the supply chain. Authorities may need

access to data for enforcement of regulations (e.g. as an alternative to reporting), and consumer and the public can get access to data depending on time constraints. There are however time constraints related to the access to the data.

Table 17 Traceability data usage example

Supply chain roles & Actors	Raw Material Provider (PR): Hermes	Transport Service Provider (SR): Råfisklaget	Trader (AR) auction: Råfisklaget	Trader (AR) contract: ScanFish	Exporter/Importer (AR): ScanFish	Transport Service Provider (SR): -	Storage Provider (SR):Troms fryse-terminal	Processor (PR): Espersen	Quality Inspector (AR): -	Retailer (PR): -	Consumer /Public (OR): -	Authority (OR): Fiskeri-direktoratet/Mattilsynet
Purpose	Traceability	Traceability	Traceability	Traceability	Traceability	Traceability	Traceability	Traceability Analyses	Traceability	Traceability	Public info	Enforcement
Other condition – Time constraints	Unlimited	< 1 year	< 90 days	< 90 days	< 90 days	< 1 year	< 1 year	Unlimited	< 90 days	Unlimited	When sold by retailer	< 1 year

3.8 Data Governance implementation considerations

The implementation of the data governance policy requires organisational as well as technical solutions.

- The Data Holder organisation must acknowledge the value of data and the need for data governance, and the associated roles and responsibilities must be fulfilled.
- The Data Holder must use the data governance framework to define the access and usage rules related to datasets.
- Technical solutions must support an implementation of the data access and use rules.

In the following the latter is addressed, and the data governance policy implementation is outlined for the traceability use case. It includes high-level guidelines and rules regarding the creation, acquisition, storage, security, quality, and permissible access to and use of data.

In general, Data Consumers may **access and use overall and detailed traceability data** on the processing event **only if**

- The dataset is classified as “shared” (see Section 3.5.1)
- The Data Consumer has a role in the supply chain that qualify for access to the data source – as defined in Table 16 in Section 3.7.2. The allowed actions must be R (for read) both for the overall (O) and detailed (D) data.
- The planned use of the data complies with the usage rules defined in Table 17 in Section 3.7.2. Purpose may for example be “traceability”, and time constraints cannot be broken.

Below is an example access and usage policy for Processor specifying allowed access and use of *sourcing event data*, showing the attributes involved, concrete implementation pattern and a machine-readable policy.

Attributes involved with value examples:

- Data Consumer:
 - Supply_chain_role = “Processor”
 - Actor = Processor’s organisation
 - User= UserID
- Context (of shared data):
 - Process_step = “sourcing”
 - Event_type = “sourcing”
 - Actor = Raw Material Provider’s organisation
- Supply Chain:
 - Supply_chain_ID = “identifier”
 - Supply_chain_members = LIST {Actor-1, Actor-2, ..., Actor-n} where the Actors are all participants in the supply chain
- Resource:
 - Dataset_type = “sourcing event”
 - Data_classification = “shared”
 - Data_content_classification = “event data”
 - Data_content_classification = “catch data”
 - Data_content_classification = “fishing vessel data”
 - Data_content_classification = “Product data”
- Action:
 - Allowed actions on Resource for DataConsumer. Supply_chain_role = “R: O+D”

- Usage:
 - Purpose="traceability"
 - Time constraint = "unlimited"

Example of a concrete implementation pattern:

1. Authenticate user
 - OAuth 2.0 / OpenID Connect
2. Assign role(s)
 - Data_sharing_role= "Data Consumer"
 - Supply_chain_role = "Processor"
3. Attach attributes
 - organisation_id
 - certification_status
 - approved_purposes
4. Evaluate ABAC rules
 - Policy engine decides allow/deny
5. Log decision
 - Full audit trail (who, what, why)

Example Policy (machine readable):

ALLOW access IF

Data Consumer.Supply_chain_role IN {Raw Material Provider, Trader, Exporter/Importer, Transport Service Provider, Storage Provider, Processor, Quality Inspector, Authority, Regulator}

AND Data Consumer.organisation IN Supply Chain.Supply_chain_members

AND Resource.Data_classification = "shared"

AND Action.Access_and_manipulation_right = "R: O+D" FOR Data Consumer.Supply_chain_role

AND Usage.purpose = "traceability"

AND current_date < usage.time_constraint

4 Conclusion

This report has developed a generic data governance framework to support secure, trustworthy, and purpose-based data sharing. It brings together roles, responsibilities, processes, dataset classifications, access and usage rules, and machine-readable Data Sharing Agreements, and demonstrates their practical application through a fish supply-chain traceability use case. By integrating hybrid RBAC–ABAC authorisation, data-quality and interoperability guidelines, and security measures, the report provides an implementable model for enabling end-to-end traceability while maintaining data sovereignty and regulatory compliance.

Future work will focus on validating and refining the framework with other use cases to ensure its applicability and robustness in different data-sharing scenarios. In particular, we plan to advance the design and implementation of data-sharing solutions for the fishery and aquaculture domain, including deployment-ready governance mechanisms, technical components, and machine-readable policies that support operational data exchange across actors in real environments.

This report has a focus on data governance responsibilities, actions and solutions. To implement data governance, there is however also a need for changes in the organisations of the Data Holders so that they can fill the responsibilities of the roles identified in Section 2.1. (Al-Ruithe and Benkhelifa, 2017) identifies barriers and success factors for the implementation of cloud data governance that also may be of relevance to data governance for data sharing in general. Barriers to be mitigated are among others:

- **Organisation barriers** like the prioritisation of data governance, the acknowledgement of data as strategic and valuable assets, and the effectuation of data governance activities.
- **Cultural barriers** such as the lack of a culture for data governance and a resistance to change.
- **Human barriers** such as lack of people, skills and experiences.
- **Knowledge barriers** regarding how to implement data governance.
- **Functional barriers** like the lack of a data governance policy to follow and related procedures, processes roles and responsibilities.
- **Technological barriers** due to the complex technical implementation of data governance when data are stored, processed and shared with others.
- **Financial barriers** like costs.

Due to the above, further work on the implementation of data governance must also address the organisational, cultural, human and knowledge barriers. Hopefully, this report can support a mitigation of some of the functional and technical barriers, while a recognition of the value of data may justify the costs.

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